

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE BANDONGAN METHOD IN THE STUDY OF *FIQH* BOOKS AT THE RIYADHUL AWAMIL BOARDING SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Boarding school is an institution of education in Indonesia and can contribute to the development of human resources and education for the general public in Indonesia. One of them is a boarding school in Banten Province, Serang city, named Riyadhul Awamil. Riyadhul Lamil Islamic Boarding School has always kept its commitment to producing cadres of the Ummah and cadres of the nation to make the human resources in it, especially as the next generation of 'alimin ulama' and generally able to practice the results of their learning in everyday life. The purpose of this study was to determine the implementation, the ability of students, and the implementation of the bandongan method in the study of *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School. This study uses a descriptive qualitative research method whose results are obtained through interviews and field observations. In the implementation of the bandongan strategy in the study of the book of *fiqh* at the Riyadhul layil Islamic boarding school, it was carried out well and there was practice from the theory contained in the contents of the *fiqh* so that it could be easily understood and understood by the students

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1. INTRODUCTION

Islamic education in Indonesia has been born since the entry of Islam to Indonesia, in the early stages of Islamic education started from personal and collective contact between preachers (educators) and students¹. After a Muslim community association was formed in an area, they began to build a mosque. Mosques by people who are Muslim are considered places of worship and education.² The mosque is an Islamic educational institution that first appeared next to the residence of the ulama or missionary. After that, other Islamic educational institutions emerged, one of which was Islamic boarding schools. Islamic boarding schools are essentially the

¹ Y Chairiyah, "Sejarah Perkembangan Sistem Pendidikan Madrasah Sebagai Lembaga Pendidikan Islam," *MA'ALIM: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* (2021),

² M Anshori and B E Wardana, "Implementasi Metode Bandongan Dan Metode Sorogan Dalam Pembelajaran Kitab Kuning Di Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida'Dusun Rambeanak 2 Desa ...," *Seminar Nasional Paedagoria 2* (2022): 190–200.

same as mosques, namely as a place to study religious knowledge.³ Pesantren is a vehicle for students (students who study in the pesantren environment) to develop and actualize themselves in social life⁴. This is the result of the transformation process to prepare the youth generation as cadres of the ummah and the nation who know. The provision of knowledge is useful in living the life of society, nation, and state.

From the description above, the author can conclude that Islamic boarding schools are one of the educational institutions in Indonesia, and have been proven to make a full contribution to the formation of community character in Indonesia. It was proven at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School in Curug District, Serang City. The students at the Islamic boarding school have very good characters, this is inseparable from the implementation of their learning outcomes.⁵

From the Dutch colonial era to the present day. At the time of independence, pesantren had an important role as an Islamic educational institution and could provide new alternatives for the learning system in Islamic education in Indonesia⁶. The formation of the character of a santri can not be separated from the role of educators (kyai), in the teaching process offered using effective learning methods. There are still many Islamic boarding schools that maintain classical methods. Because the classical method has its characteristics. So that until now it still exists, it is applied and even becomes an important element in traditional pesantren or *salaf*. One of them is the bandongan method.⁷ The bandongan or *wetonan* method is a teaching method in which the teacher reads, translates, explains, and writes Islamic books in Arabic while a group of students listens to them paying attention to their books and making notes (both meaning and description) about words or thoughts. the hard one⁸.

Islamic boarding school is located in the capital city of Banten province, namely the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School. Since its establishment in 2005, the pesantren still uses the bandongan method as a teaching and learning method for books. Book studies that use the bandongan method include the study of nahwu Sharaf books, *fiqh* books, interpretations of the Qur'an, hadith books, and so on. Of the various book studies that use the bandongan method at the Islamic boarding school, the authors choose one of them as research material, namely the study of *fiqh*. For researchers, the study of *fiqh* is an important science to learn for people who embrace Islam. Because every human movement needs the science of *fiqh* that animates it. For example, being aware that when humans want to worship their Lord (Allah SWT) they need to know the materials and mechanisms that have been regulated in *fiqh*. That is, every human being wants to perform worship to Allah SWT some procedures must be followed in each of its stages.⁹

Based on the results of the author's research observations, in the application of the bandongan method in the study of *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic boarding school, there are interesting things. At the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School, it is not just theory that is discussed, however, students or students are required to practice their learning outcomes in everyday life.

Based on the description above, the authors get an important problem. They are interested in carrying out research activities at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School with the title "Implementation of the Bandongan Method in the Study of the Book of *Fiqh* at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School". The research objectives include: *First*, to find out how the implementation of the bandongan method in the study *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School; *Second*, to find out how the *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School; and *third*, determine the ability of students in applying the science of studying *fiqh* in daily life at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School.

³ E Nurhidin, "Pesantren-Based School Culture Development: The Practice Of Kitab Kuning Learning In School," *At-Tarbiyat: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* (2022).

⁴ Mahfud Ifendi, "Metode Pembelajaran Kitab Kuning Di Pondok Pesantren Sunan Drajad Banjarwati Lamongan," *Al-Tarbawi Al-Haditsah: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* 6, no. 2 (2021): 85.

⁵ F Fakhurrazi and S Sebgag, "Methods of Learning Kitab Kuning for Beginners in Islamic Boarding School (Dayah)," *Nazhruna: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* (2020)

⁶ C Muali et al., "Pesantren Dan Millennial Behaviour: Tantangan Pendidikan Pesantren Dalam Membina Karakter Santri Milenial," ... : *Jurnal Pendidikan ...* (2020)

⁷ Fahmi, Muhtarom, Yusuf, Suharsono, Suharsono. Syaefudin, "Lahjah Arabiyah Lahjah Arabiyah," *Lahjah Arabiyah* 1, no. 2 (2020): 105–119.

⁸ H Indra, "Pendidikan Islam Membangun Akhlak Generasi Bangsa," *Ta'dibuna: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* (2019).

⁹ Muhsin Aseri, "Manajemen Pembelajaran Fiqih Di Sekolah Dan Madrasa Bagi Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam," *Al-Madrasah: Jurnal Pendidikan Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* 6, no. 2 (2022): 229.

2. METHOD

Explaining This study entitled "Implementation of the Bandungan Method in the Study of the Book of *Fiqh* at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School" uses qualitative research, namely descriptive research, so that the data collected is in the form of words or pictures. Qualitative research does not generalize but emphasizes the information aspect in the field so that it becomes a meaning. (Sugiyono, 2017) the stages in data collection carried out by researchers are interviews and observations. So that researchers become easily analyze and describe the results of their research. The stages that must be taken in conducting qualitative research are: 1. Data reduction; Reducing data means summarizing, choosing the main things, focusing on the important things, and looking for themes and patterns. Thus the data that has been reduced will provide a clearer picture and make it easier for researchers to carry out further data collection. And reducing data can also be helped with electronic equipment¹⁰. 2. Presentation of data; After reducing the data, the next step is to present the data. Because it will make it easier for researchers to understand what is going on and then plan further work based on what has been understood¹¹. 3. Conclusion drawing/verification; The final stage in analyzing qualitative data is drawing conclusions and verification. The first conclusion made is only temporary and will change if no strong and supporting evidence is found at the next stage of data collection. On the other hand, if the conclusions made in the first stage are supported by concrete and consistent evidence, then the conclusions drawn are conclusions that can be trusted¹². The number of students in this boarding school is 229 people. So, in this case, the author took a sample of five people as representatives in this study with a simple random sampling technique.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The History of the Establishment of the Riyadhul Awami Islamic Boarding School

The results of an interview with Abdurrahman, the chairman of the board at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic Boarding School, KH Syafrudin established a boarding school called *Riyadhul 'Awamil* which is located in Kp. Seven Rt. 006 Rw. 002 Sukajaya Village, Curug District, Serang City, Banten. The history of the establishment of the salafiyyah Islamic boarding school *Riyadhul 'Awamil*, is closely related to the beginning when KH Syafrudin married Umi Mahfudhoh around 2003' after marrying KH Syafruddin and his wife settled in Kp. Seven and founded a boarding school called *Riyadhul 'Awamil*.

The name *Riyadhul 'Awamil* itself was a gift from a professor from the Baros sub-district named KH Salim (late). The name *Riyadhul 'Awamil* means "***The Garden of the Charity***". The reason the teacher gave the name *Riyadhul 'Awamil* is that KH Salim (late) has a hut called *Riyadhul 'Awamil* too.

KH Syafrudin founded the *Riyadhul 'Awamil* because he wanted to change the lifestyle of the surrounding community and it can be said that at that time the people here had an unfavorable lifestyle. Islamic Boarding School *Riyadhul 'Awamil* is hoped that the surrounding community can better understand the religion of Islam and be able to apply it in everyday life. He was not only a teacher or professor of students at this Islamic boarding school but also a teacher for mothers and fathers in an assembly.

The location is strategic, quite conducive, and comfortable for learning activities. Because it is located not far from the highway that is passed by the city bus line. However, the atmosphere is quite conducive and comfortable for teaching and learning activities because the environment is beautiful.

3.2. The Study of Books

Islamic Boarding School *Riyadhul 'Awamil* is an Islamic boarding school at the Ibtida stage, which means a boarding school for beginners. In boarding school, Riyadhul Layil not only learns the yellow book but learn the science of the Qur'an. Here are some fan/branches of knowledge that are taught at the Riyadhul Lawahil Islamic Boarding School, as follows:

¹⁰ Robert M Kosanke, "POLA AJARAN SALAFI PADA PEMBELAJARAN FIQIH DI SEKOLAH DASAR ISLAM SALMAN AL-FARISI KOTA BEKASI" 5 (2019): 19–28.

¹¹ Aseri, "Manajemen Pembelajaran Fiqih Di Sekolah Dan Madrasa Bagi Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam."

¹² F A I Universitas and Hasyim Asy, "MADRASAH ALIYAH SEBLAK KWARON JOMBANG Lely Sansiska Ningrum * Guru Dalam Membentuk Metode Pelajaran Tidak Banyak Yang Bisa Menguasai Tentang Metode Pengajaran Yang Baik Untuk Peserta Didik Sehingga Mengurangi Semangat Belajar Siswa . Selain Itu Sebagai Se" (n.d.).

Table 1. Table List of Books that are taught.

No	Branch of	Book
1.	<i>Fiqh of</i>	Fathul Mu'in, Sittin Mas'alah, Riyadhul Ba'diyah, Qurrotul Uyyun, Safinatun Najah and 'Uqudul Zain
2.	Nahwu	Awamil Mandaya, Jurumiah, Al-fiyah ibn Malik
3.	Sharaf	Matan Bina, Tasrif (Sharaf Total)
4.	Tafsir	Tafsir Al-Jalalen
5.	Adab/Akhlak	Ta'lim Muta'alim
6.	Tawhid	Qotrul Ghois
7.	Hadith	Durrotun Nashihin
8.	Qur'an	Al-Qur'an

Some of the books mentioned above are the main books that are studied by students every time. It's different if in the month of Ramadan, usually at the *Riyadhul 'Awamil* holding a routine market study activity every year in the month of Ramadan, the book being studied is the book of a Hadith Science fan.

3.3. Number of Santri

The number of students in the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School is quite large and the majority are inhabited by female students. The details of the number of students at the Riyadhul Lawahil Islamic Boarding School are as follows:

Table 2. List of the number of students

No	Gender	Total
1.	Male	76 people
2.	Female	153 people
Total Total 229		people

Interview with the chairman of the board at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic boarding school, the number of students in the table is only temporary. Because every year there are incoming and outgoing students. Even more, people are coming in than people are leaving.

3.3. Recitation Schedule at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School

Every Islamic boarding school must have a recitation schedule that must be followed by all students. Riyadhul Layil Islamic boarding school also has a regular schedule at any time. The following are the recitation times:

Table 3. List of recitation times

No.	Day	Time	of the Book
1.	Monday	Ba'da Subuh 05.00 - the end	of the Qur'an
		Morning at 08.00 - finished	Fathul Mu'in, Alfiyah Ibn Malik

		Ba'da Dzuhur at 13.30 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Asr at 17.00 - finished	Tafsir Jalalen
		Ba'da Magrib at 18.20 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Isha at 20.00 - finished	Khataman Qur'an, Mana'iqib Jawahirul Ma'ani, Dalail
2.	Tuesday	Ba'da Subuh at 05.00 - finished	Al-Qur'an
		Morning at 08.00 - finish	weekly recitation with mothers
		Ba'da Dzuhur at 13.30 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Asr at 17.00 - finished	Tafsir Jalalen
		Ba'da Magrib at 18.20 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Isha at 20.00 - finished	Khataman Qur'an, Riyadhul Ba'diah, Sittin Mas'alah, Fathul Mu'in
3.	Wednesday	Ba'da Fajr at 05.00 - finished	Al-Qur'an
		Morning at 08.00 - finished	Fathul Mu'in, Alfiyah Ibn Malik
		Ba'da Dzuhur at 13.30 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Asr at 17.00 - finished	Tafsir Jalalen
		Ba'da Magrib at 18.20 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Isya at 20.00 - finished	Khatam Qur'an, Matan Bina, Qotrul Ghois, Tasrif (Sharaf Total)
4.	Thursday	Ba'da Subuh at 05.00 - finished	Al-Qur'an
		Morning at 08.00-finish	Fathul Mu'in, Al- fiyah Ibn Malik

		Ba'da Dzuhur at 13.30 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Asr at 17.00 - finished	Tafsir Jalalen
		Ba'da Magrib at 18.20 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Isya at 20.00 - finished	Yasinan, Manaqib Jawahirul Ma'ani, Marhabanan
5.	Friday	Ba'da Subuh 05.00 - finished	Holiday
		Morning at 09.00 - finished the	routine study with the gentlemen
		Ba'da Dzuhur at 13.30 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Asr at 17.00-end of	holiday
		Ba'da Magrib at 18.20 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Isha at 20.00 - finished	Muhadoroh
6.	Saturday	Ba'da Subuh at 05.00 - finished	Al-Qur'an
		Morning at 08.00 - finish	Fathul Mu'in, Qurrotul Uyun, Uqudul Zain, Safinatun Najah, Alfiyah Ibn Malik, Durrotun Nashihin
		Ba'da Dzuhur at 13.30 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Asr at 17.00 - finished	Tafsir Jalalen
		Ba'da Magrib at 18.20 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
		Ba'da Isha at 20.00 - finished	Khataman Qur'an, Riyadhul Ba'diah, Sittin Mas'alah, Fathul Mu'in
7.	Sunday	Ba'da Subuh 05.00 - finished	Al-Qur'an

Morning at 08.00 - finish	Fathul Mu'in, Qurrotul Uyun, Uqudul Zain, Safinatun Najah, Alfiyah Ibn Malik, Durrotun Nashihin
Ba'da Dzuhur at 13.30 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
Ba'da Asr at 17.00 - finished	Tafsir Jalalen
Ba'da Magrib at 18.20 - finished	Awamil, Jurumiah, Matan Bina
Ba'da Isha 20.00 hours - finished	Khataman Qur'an, Ta'lim Muta'alim, Al-fiyah Ibn Malik

3.4. Recitation Schedule at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School

In the author's observations during the research, in the process of the bandongan system at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School, first, the cleric reads the lafadz of the study *fiqh* that will be studied, namely the books of Riyadhul Ba'diyah, Sittin Mas'alah and Fathul Mu'in, then translated using Javanese, which makes the kyai's reference source why when translating this book is translated into Javanese this is in line with scholars, especially in Java, Banten, because seeing from the high priest of Indonesia, namely Sheikh Nawawi Al-Bantani from birth used Javanese language and translated his books using Javanese to his students.¹³ After the kyai reads, translates and then the kyai explains the contents of the *fiqh* studied using a mixed language between Indonesian, Sundanese, and Javanese Serang, the last thing to do is have a rereading session for his students in front of the kyai and all the students. It aims to determine the focus of the students during the recitation and to know their ability as well as to train the students in reading the books that are read. The task of students during the recitation process is only to take notes, pay attention and listen to the material being delivered.¹⁴

In general, the use of the bandongan method in Islamic boarding schools begins with the arrangement of the study/recitation room by forming a neat sitting formation, usually, the kyai sits in front using a chair and the book is placed on the table, then the students surround the kyai. The sitting formation as stated by Nurcholis Madjid aims that the students are expected to be respectful and polite when listening to the explanations given by the kyai¹⁵.

The methods that are often used in Islamic boarding schools include sorogan, bandongan, or wetonan, deliberation, memorization, and learn.¹⁶ Means that many methods are used when teaching and learning in Islamic boarding schools. Referring to Mastuhu's words, the name bandongan is already familiar to the ears of the students in Indonesia. Because the bandongan method is one of the methods used by teachers or kyai in carrying out teaching and learning activities in Islamic boarding schools. The bandongan or *wetonan* method is a teaching method in which the teacher reads, translates, explains, and writes Islamic books in Arabic while a group of students listens to them paying attention to their own books and making notes (both meaning and

¹³ R S Y Zebua and S Sunarti, "The Strategy Of Islamic Character Education With Role Model And Habituation Method On Online Learning," *Ta'dib: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* (2020).

¹⁴ M R Habibullah and H Nihayah, "Metodologi Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam Untuk Kaum Lansia Di Pondok Pesantren Lansia Al Hidayah Kelurahan Doromukti Kecamatan Tuban Kabupaten ...," ... *AUFA: JURNAL PENDIDIKAN ...* (2019).

¹⁵ Ratih Miftakhur Rosidah and Rinaningsih Rinaningsih, "Implementasi Metode Bandongan Untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Peserta Didik Pada Materi Asam Basa," *PENDIPA Journal of Science Education* 6, no. 2 (2022): 594–598.

¹⁶ Fil Waadhi and Muhammad Farid Wajidi, "Almufi Jurnal Pendidikan (AJP) Implementasi Metode Sorogan Pada Mata Pelajaran Fiqih Dalam" 2, no. 2 (2022).

description) about words or thoughts. the hard one.¹⁷ In this case, Dofier redefined that the bandongan method is a group learning method and is classical, meaning that all students are assigned to certain classes¹⁸. In the implementation of the bandongan method of studying *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School, it is not much different from the definition described above.¹⁹ Based on the author's research, the use of the bandongan method at the Riyadhul Lawahil Islamic Boarding School as the main method for conducting a study of *fiqh*²⁰. This is an effort by the teacher or kyai so that the students at the Islamic boarding school can understand and practice the results of their learning in their daily lives. In practice, the kyai does not only read, translate, and explain, but the kyai does practice when the recitation activities take place. Because, according to the kyai when interviewed "it is not enough when studying *fiqh* only to give examples of the theory, but there must be examples of practices that students really need to know". According to Cak Nur, *fiqh* defines *fiqh* as a set of amaliah laws which are practiced and prescribed in Islam. The science of *fiqh* is an Islamic science that discusses the laws that regulate the pattern of human relations: *hablum mina Allah*, *hablum Minan Nash*, and *hablum Minal Alam*.²¹ Through learning *fiqh*, it is hoped that students will not come out of the circle of religious norms and carry out according to the rules of Islamic law²². Basically, *fiqh* is an Islamic law that must be owned by a mukhalaf Muslim. So, of course, the goal is identical to the Islamic religious law itself. Because the object is all the actions of converts in carrying out their daily activities in order to educate their spiritual and soul. This means that the science of *fiqh* has a noble purpose for the people who run it. It's just that the purpose of the science of *fiqh* is more detaile and firm than the goals of Islamic law.²³

The general objectives of the study of *jurisprudence* taught using the bandongan method at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School are as follows: a. So that students have a basic knowledge of *fiqh* themselves; b. So that students can read, translate and explain *fiqh*; and c. So that students understand the science of *fiqh*. As well as specific objectives including: a. Practice their knowledge while worshiping Allah; b. To transfer their knowledge to the common people; c. Make the science of *fiqh* a break in all actions that are prohibited in Islamic law.²⁴

Each learning method used by the teacher when delivering the material to his students must have advantages and disadvantages of the method. The advantages and disadvantages of using the bandongan method²⁵

Table 4. Advantages and disadvantages of the bandongan method

No.	Strengths	Disadvantages
1.	It is faster and more practical to teach a large number of students	The method is considered slow and traditional because the delivery of the material is often repeated
2.	The material taught is often repeated, making it easier for students to understand	It Teachers are more active than students because the learning process is one path (monologue)
3.	Very efficient in teaching the accuracy of sentences that are difficult to learn.	There is no dialogue between teachers and students, so students get bored quickly.

¹⁷ Indra, "Pendidikan Islam Membangun Akhlak Generasi Bangsa."

¹⁸ Waadhi and Wajidi, "Almufi Jurnal Pendidikan (AJP) Implementasi Metode Sorogan Pada Mata Pelajaran Fiqih Dalam."

¹⁹ A Z A Arief, "Nilai Salaf Dalam Tradisi Pendidikan Islam Di Pesantren Modern (Studi Lapangan Pondok Pesantren Darul 'Ulum Jombang)," *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai* (2021),

²⁰ M Anshori and B E Wardana, "Implementasi Metode Bandongan Dan Metode Sorogan Dalam Pembelajaran Kitab Kuning Di Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida'Dusun Rambeanak 2 Desa . . .," *Seminar Nasional Paedagogia 2* (2022): 292–302.

²¹ Waadhi and Wajidi, "Almufi Jurnal Pendidikan (AJP) Implementasi Metode Sorogan Pada Mata Pelajaran Fiqih Dalam."

²² Aris Aris and Syukron Syukron, "Perbandingan Metode Bandongan Dan Sorogan Dalam Memahami Kitab Safinatunnajah," *Tsaqafatuna 2*, no. 1 (2020): 1–10.

²³ L Khasanah, "KONSEP PEMIKIRAN PENDIDIKAN ISLAM MENURUT KH. HASYIM ASY'ARI," *QALAM: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* (2020).

²⁴ N Qosim, "Manajemen Kurikulum Pendidikan Pesantren Salaf," *At-Ta'lim: Jurnal Pendidikan* (2019).

²⁵ Ifendi, "Metode Pembelajaran Kitab Kuning Di Pondok Pesantren Sunan Drajad Banjarwati Lamongan."

3.5. Implementation of the Bandongan Method in the Study of the Book of *Fiqh* at the Riyadhul Awamil Islamic Boarding School.

The results of the research on October 4, 2022, entitled "Implementation of the Bandongan method in the study of the book *of fiqh* at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic Boarding School."

The implementation of the bandongan method in the study of *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School has several ways of delivering it. In general, reading, translating, and explaining is something that a teacher or kyai must do when delivering the material. And as a student, it is enough to take notes, pay attention and just listen. However, it is important to know that in the application of the bandongan method at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic Boarding School there are strategies carried out by the kyai so that students can focus and understand what they are learning. The strategy used in the delivery is that the kyai always provides humor to the students when explaining the material. This is one of the kyai's ways so that students do not get bored easily in learning and always give an appeal or warning to their students to stay focused because the kyai always considers learning the science of *fiqh* very important and must be owned by all Muslim people who live on this earth.. Moreover, people who have the title of santri kyai always emphasize being able to transfer their knowledge to the general public when they are already in the community.

For the time of learning, it is done every day in the morning and evening on Tuesday and Sunday. However, the authors examined only 3 books, namely Fathul Mu'in, Riyadhul Ba'diah and Sittin Mas'alah.

The results of the application of the results of the study of the book *of fiqh* using the bandongan method at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic boarding school based on the results of observations and interviews, always emphasize the aspect of understanding that has been conveyed by the material and students are required to be able to re-read the material of the book of *fiqh* during the study. The bandongan method applied in the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic boarding school has been designed as best as possible by the kyai. It aims to make students able to understand the content of the material that has been taught. After all, students are able to understand all the material, students are required to implement and practice it in their daily lives.

So, the implementation of the bandongan method in the study of *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic Boarding School can be carried out properly. The strategy in implementing the bandongan method of studying the book *of fiqh* is not only that but there is the role of a kyai who always prays for his students and motivates them to keep on learning and not stop learning. Because of the hope built by the kyai at the Riyadhul Lail Islamic boarding school, at least the students can practice their learning outcomes in their daily lives and the high hopes of all students become 'alimin ulama, the successors of the struggle of the ulama in Indonesia and always put forward Islamic values.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the data obtained by the author from interviews and observations in the field, it can be concluded that the implementation of the bandongan method in the study *fiqh* at the Riyadhul Lamil Islamic Boarding School is carried out in the morning and evening. the bandongan method which is taught to its students is in accordance with the theory of implementing the bandongana method in general and its implementation is very effective. Implementation of the bandongan method in the study *fiqh* at Riyadhul Layil Islamic boarding schools is the main method in conveying the study *of fiqh* and processed as best as possible by the kyai so that students can understand and repeat reading their books from the results of the *fiqh* that he conveys. The ability of students after studying the book *of fiqh* at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School using the bandongan method is very good. As for the factors: *first*, the style of delivery of the kyai in the application of the bandongan method is very light and logical, so that students at the Riyadhul Layil Islamic Boarding School can understand *fiqh* easily and can apply the results of their *fiqh* in their daily lives. *Second*, the kyai always prays for his students and motivates them to keep on learning and not stop learning.

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